

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B149
Date: 13 Dec 2005
Take Off: 11:59:13
Landing: 16:10:13
Flight Time: 4h11m00

Campaign: Buncefield Smoke Experiment
Operating Area: South East England around Hemel Hemstead

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Graham Morgan	Directflight
3	CCM	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manger	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Paul James	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office
9	Filters / PSAP	Stuart Heath	FAAM
10	SWS	Dave Kindred	Met Office
11	AMS	James Allen	Manchester University
12	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
13	CCM training	Joanne Green	Directflight
14			
15			
16			
17			
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19			

Flight Track:

B149 Track 13-DEC-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b149
 Date: 13 Dec 2005
 Project: Buncefield Smoke Experiment
 Location: Central England

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
114445		engine start	-.39 kft	125	
114612		inu to nav	-.39 kft	125	
114842		taxy start	-.39 kft	099	
114850		camera recording	-.39 kft	062	
115913		T/O	-.39 kft	213	
120444		asp open	9.0 kft	231	
120839	122925	Run 1	9.0 kft	167	
122155		Run 1	9.0 kft	090 C	
122322		jw nevz zero	9.0 kft	087	
123107		qnh	7.1 kft	119	1039
123240	130402	Run 2	5.3 kft	272	
124030		Run 2	5.3 kft	295 C	
124212		Run 2	5.3 kft	341	plume top
124452		Run 2	5.3 kft	328	interrupt for orbit
124905		Run 2	5.3 kft	351	resume
125318		Run 2	5.3 kft	345 B	
130729	132826	Run 3	4.3 kft	172	5000 ft
131254		qnh	4.3 kft	167	1040
131705		Run 3	4.3 kft	153 B	
132308		Run 3	4.3 kft	154	top of plume
132534		Run 3	4.3 kft	089 C	at last entry
132847		psap interrupted	4.3 kft	119	
133125	134907	Run 4	3.3 kft	284	
133631		Run 4	3.3 kft	304	Point C
134534		Run 4	3.3 kft	352 B	
135132	141244	Run 5	2.3 kft	200	starts at b
140121		Run 5	2.3 kft	153 C	
140956		Run 5	2.3 kft	087 D	
141702	143552	Run 6	1.3 - 1.4 kft	297	
143227		Run 6	1.3 kft	320	
143950	145628	Run 7	3.3 kft	142	
144303		Run 7	3.3 kft	153 B	
144422		Run 7	3.3 kft	156	psap off
144453		Run 7	3.3 kft	157	psap on
144837		Run 7	3.3 kft	153 C	
144849		Run 7	3.3 kft	125	plume
145626		Run 7	3.3 kft	089	
145822	151325	Run 8	3.8 kft	284	
150544		Run 8	3.8 kft	285 C	
151810	152410	Run 8	3.9 kft	359	resumed
153634	153858	Run 9	3.4 kft	162	
153930	154132	Run 10	2.9 kft	166	
154210	154342	Run 11	2.4 kft	266	
154348	154640	Run 12	2.4 - 1.9 kft	041	
154815	155051	Run 13	1.4 kft	309	
155347	155517	Run 14	1.4 kft	049	
161013		Land	-.32 kft	214	

B149 Track 13-DEC-05

Fire Smoke

B149 – 13th December 2005

Flight path way points:

- A. Daventry Beacon 52 10N 01 10 W
- B. Woodley Beacon 51 25N 00 50 W
- C. Midhurst Beacon 51 05N 00 40 W
- D. Mayfield Beacon 51 00N 00 05E

1200	Transit to Daventry Beacon	30
1230	Straight and level from A to D at 9000 ft	30
1300	Return straight and level from D to A at 8000 ft	30
1330	Straight and level from A to D at 7000 ft	30
1400	Return straight and level from D to A at 6000 ft	30
1430	Straight and level from A to D at 5000 ft	30
1500	Return straight and level from D to A at 4000 ft	30
1530	Straight and level from A to D at 3000 ft	30
1600	Return straight and level from D to A at 2000 ft	30
1630	Transit to Cranfield	30
1700	Land at Cranfield	30

Mission Scientist debrief

B149 – 13th December 2005

Fire Smoke Sortie

Mission Scientist – Clare Lee

This was the second flight to study the smoke from the Buncfield fuel depot fire at Hemel Hempstead. A four point leg (Daventry Beacon – Woodley Beacon – Midhurst Beacon – Mayfield Beacon) was set up such that we could operate in the congested airways in the SE. Initially we were given priority E clearance which is slightly higher than general aviation, but due to the congestion there were occasions when air traffic had to deviate us from the flight track and the pilots had to make evasive maneuvers. Scientifically this area of operation should only be considered in exceptional circumstances. Towards the end of the flight, higher priorities were given such that we could operate right over the source of the fire.

After take off the smoke plume over the source could be seen clearly, which was been capped by an inversion. Generally there was 7/8 to 8/8 Cu below clearing to the North and 2/8 to 3/8 of thin Ci above. A run at 9000ft was made to determine a visual location of the plume. The plume was a narrow strip extending away from the source crossing the flight track at the Midhurst Beacon turning point. At the end of the run a procedural turn and descent (non-profile) was made. A reciprocal run from Mayfield towards Daventry beacon was made at 6000ft, still above the Cu cloud tops. The local pressure setting was 1039mb. Just after Midhurst turning point the aircraft was visually over the plume. The cloud physics and core chemistry instruments did not record any significant changes. The end of the run was terminated early to optimize the time at the plume area. A non-profile descent to 5000ft was made and reciprocal run towards Mayfield. The Cu tops were approximately 300ft below. At 5000ft the very narrow top of the plume was measured by PCSAP and the CO concentrations at 13:22 at Midhurst beacon increased. This run was also terminated early for a descent and turn to 4000ft. A marked inversion was seen by core chemistry during the descent. A reciprocal leg at 4000ft in the Cu tops was made towards Daventry. Just before Midhurst at 13:36 with Cu tops 50ft below, the aircraft entered the plume for approx 2 minutes, showing an increase in CO and PCASP concentrations. This run was also ended early. A turn and descent to 3000ft was made, with both core chemistry and AMS noting boundary layer conditions. At 3000ft a run was made in the bottoms of the Cu towards Mayfield. The bottom of the plume was measured at 14:01 just SE of Midhurst. At 1403, due South of Hemel Hempstead, a greater increase in CO and PCASP were seen. The run was extended East past Mayfield to determine the horizontal extent. At the end of the run a turn and descent to 2000ft was made, followed by a run back to Daventry. At 14:26 the plume was visually seen above and small rise in CO and PCASP was noted. There was a particularly large amount of air traffic at 2000ft. A staggered ascent to 4000ft was made and reciprocal run to Mayfield was made. At Mayfield only residual increases were seen. The main plume had moved further East to 51.0N, 0.2W measured at 14:50. A reciprocal leg to Midhurst was made at 4500ft above the Cu tops. No increase in CO or PSCAP was seen. At Midhurst a new heading direct to Cranfield was made at 4500ft to pass close to Hemel Hempstead. At 15:35 the aircraft priority was changed to enable flights over the source. At 15:45 a perpendicular pass through the plume close to the source at 2500ft was made, with PCASP, CO and AMS observing increased readings. At 15:48

a run along in the plume at 2000ft towards the source was made. At 1553 a second run was made along the plume at 2000ft. During this run the largest readings were observed with PSAP, AMS, CO and the CPI observed soot approximately 10 - 50 micron in diameter.

The aircraft was then recovered to Cranfield.

Instrument status

Cloud physics – OK

PSAP – OK

Core chemistry – OK

SWS – OK

CPI – OK

AMS – OK

Filters – OK

Note the standard filters and those from AMS was police escorted to government labs for analysis.

ARIES – OK (on for training with covers on)

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.149**

 Date **13/12/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:00					Take Off Cranfield.
12:05					can see plume at ~10 o'clock. Extending ahead. V. limited in vertical extent few left. only.
120839	R1	9000ft.	166	51.710.9	Run start. Running ^{nearly} parallel but slow interception with downwind. wind 11ms ⁻¹ 12.7° from from eye. estimating plume top at 600ft. at point C. plume appears to be narrow. Have gone over top of it. winds 12ms ⁻¹ 14.7° 03 50-85, 10 116.5
122137		9000ft.	087	51.010.5W	
122925	Rland.	9000ft.		51.010.1E	ending run. descending to 6000ft. not profile descent: as turning whilst descending. 7g ⁺ W below, 21g G above. press. setting 1039 mb.
123240	R2	6000ft.			run from D to A. 20 → 120 counts. increase in aerosol.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123540				51.0/0.1	Plane W top. (8/8) wind 010 27knts aircraft- wind 13ms ⁻¹ 22° can see plane ahead. from 10 o'clock to 3 o'clock. 03 50.4, 10 121.31 all ambient. 502. 0.58
123856					can see plane strip ahead.
124022		6000ft.		51.0/0.6	At point C turning. wind 17ms ⁻¹ 126°
124120				51.0/0.6	Over plane. SLAS PCASP steady. no changes in dem. or AMS
124210				51.1/0.6W	Over top. winds 13ms ⁻¹ 115° T 1.66, TD -20.9°
124306				51.1/0.7W	At other edge 8/8 W below, plane looks like v-dark grey patch. cloud.
124452	R2.int.				Intercepting run - left turn due to air traffic. ~45° bank angle.
124905	R2	6000ft.		51.2/0.7	Recommencing run
124957					cloud cloud 1/8 W. below, 3/8 C above.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125317		6000ft	351°		At point 6. 220knts aircraft speed. wind 11ms ⁻¹ 14° aircraft wind 24knts 1341°
125524				51.5N/10.9W	going over 7/8 W below.
130402	Rend	6000ft		52.0N/11.0W	Stopping on 10 miles short to optimise time around plume. Turning left + descending to 5000ft.
130729	R3	5000ft	169	52.0N/11.0W	37 miles from Woodley wind 13ms ⁻¹ 1352°. CO doing cal at end of runs. wind: 12ms ⁻¹ 1353° 010° 121knts
131214		5000ft	167	51.6N/10.9W	Over 7/8 W by ~ 300ft. RPSP decreased from 100 → 20 knts AMS seeing trace amount of sulphate ~ 1/2 µm normal for free trop. 03 46.7 → 10 110 ppb ↳ v. slight decrease Can see plume to right from 12 o'clock to 8 o'clock ↻ f
131612					Clear below.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131844		5000ft.	134		turn at point B appears that source is no longer emitting smoke. Can see plume ahead. in top of CU.
132054					Over 8/8 W., 4/8 Ci above definite plume
132200					midhurst way point (2) in middle of plume!
132325					PCASP 5000 cc. } sudden CO 140 ppb. } peak.
132406					PCASP 40 cc v. narrow plume. AMS saw blip but too short to determine anything.
132826	R3 cont.	5000ft.			End of run turning early to right. to get clear plume again. Turning left for descent to 4000ft.
133018		4300ft.			In top of CU. with change alt.
133125	R4	4000ft.			CO diary cal, O3 decrease 28-3 ppb. NOx increase ~ 4 ppb.
133357					right in top of cloud 2D seeing water drops.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133520					from 5 → 4 kft. seeing mixed inversion.
133640					soft above cloud top. edge of plume. wind: 7ms ⁻¹ / 25° 014° / 20knts.
133702					CO 140.21
133711					main plume. 2 diff layers ^{one above}
133730					point C turning.
133738					at of it now. (plume) then seeing increase in CO in large plume, but otherwise larger concs. before in main plume
133828		4000ft	341	51-1/0.6W	in cloud tops. PCA5P 203300 ~ 1/2 rim diam. const. → 2500 concs AMS not huge amount ~ 1/4 μm/m ³
134028		4000ft	341	51-2/0.7W	skirting tops of W 818. looks like just went through very top of plume only.
134517			351.		at point B.
134907	R4	4000ft		51-6 10.9W	End of run early turning + descending to 3000ft. CO increasing, O3 decreasing due to going into boundary layer. AMS large increase in sulphate according to being in boundary layer.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
135132	RS	3000ft.	201	51.6/0.8	wind 11ms ⁻¹ / 344° 03 36.7, 10 122.67 002 2.98
135254					In cloud. At bottoms of G.
135430		3000ft.	159	51.3/0.8W	Seeing fluctuations in O3 + CO amounts (100 → 140 ppb) winds 11ms ⁻¹ / 342°
135859			159	51.2/0.7W	Going into cloud. 8/8W. 10 miles to Midhurst. 03 31.2, 10 128 wind 9ms ⁻¹ 350° 001° / 13 knts.
140109				51.0/0.6	at point C. (Midhurst) have to continue leading due to aircraft
140142					Turning left onto leg. Appear to be below max 7 ppb NOx 145 ppb CO clouds 250 → 450 max AMS no real changes mainly sulphates + some
140329					wind 8ms ⁻¹ / 351 002 122

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140359					dive S of hotel Hempstead
					dwd phys. 900 → 1000
140444					CO 159.19 ↑
140522			34	51.0/1.2W	CO 166.6
					aerosol. 900 → 600
					winds 7ms ⁻¹ 15°
					008/16 knts.
140638					CO peak: 195 ppb.
					AMS seeing steady increase
					in sulphate (not discrete).
					10 possible emissions from
					London.
140813				51.0/1.0E	CO 167.9 ↓
					O3 28.8 ppb.
140943					point D.
					continuing dive E
					aerosol. 500 cc. - London poll.?
					AMS - seeing things generally
					associated with combustion.
					CO 147, O3 33.9 ppb.
141138			88	50.9/1.3	South of Gravesend.
141316				50.9/1.4	turning + descending
141702	R6	2000ft.	204		Leading back to A.
142634					CO 147.55, O3 19.8,
					SO2 2.98
					plane above.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
142737		2000ft.	337		Clear of plume above chem dropping off AMS - typical for urban pollution cloud phys: peak 1500cc. CO 150.8, O3 22.9 SO2 3.18 T 0.46, T _d -0.17°C
143230					Having to manoeuvre away from aircraft.
143558	R6 end	2000ft.	356	51.5/10.9W	Run end Increasing altitude to 3000ft.
143720		3000ft.		51.6/10.9	Climbing to 4000ft. wind 9ms ⁻¹ 1331° Top of W.
1439	R7	3820ft. 4000ft.	151		St. Run. O3 44.7, 10 112.5 SO2 1.18
144502					Increase in CO data in cloud top prob. due to convection bringing lower level up.
14:48:40				51.0/10.6	point C turning right.
14:48:48					in plume. visually only aerosol increased 20 → 40

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144943			92	51.0/0.5	NOX + SO2 increase (small) Can see more plume ahead. Maybe split in 2.
145133					In cloud - increase in 10 aerosol max. 1200 cc. <small>nam 50-760</small>
145215			91	51.0/0.2	Chem small increase NOX + SO2
145300					gone through plume out to left. In + out of cloud tops.
				51.0/0.0	winds 5ms - 355° OOT 116
145628	R7end	4000ft.		51.0/0.1	End of run, climbing to 4500 ft. AMS - increase in organics } unburned hydrocarbons. } (CO also increased + O3 decrease)
145822	R8	4500	288	50.9/0.1	Start of run from D to C. Can see plume ahead above cloud tops, 5186 above. definitely in clear air.
150131			287	50.9/0.1	cloud phys. 50cc ambient level. CO 109, O3 49.6, SO2 0.78

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	
150332		4500ft			Harder to see plume. 8/8 W below.	
150541		4500ft	331	51.0/0.5	Aft point C (Mightburst) Heading direct to Cranfield. winds 11ms ⁻¹ 18° CO 110, O3 49.6, SO2 0.67 ambient levels	
150957					Hazy - smell in cabin? ^{cloud mass} 50 → 100 cc aerosol.	
15:12:57		4500ft	0	51.3/0.6	8/8 W below.	
151325	R8 and	4500ft			For air traffic increasing to 6000ft. then will descend	
					SAMs increase in organics in plume. typical for organics on soot particles.	
151736		6000ft. 4000				descending
151810	R8	4500ft	357	51.6/0.6		Reappearance of R8. Trying to sort out permissions
153551			165		Descending in direction of hemel Hempstead.	

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153634	R9	4000ft.	162	51.9/10.5	Plane W 818.
	R9end.	4000ft.	166		end of run
		3500ft.			descending to 3500ft.
	R10st.	3500ft.	166	51.7/10.4	no increase in chem or
154132	R10end	3500ft.			a descending. to get below
					cloud.
	R11	3000ft.	267	51.6/10.5	in base cloud.
	R11end.				
154259					large rise in AMS sulphate
					descending to 2.5kft.
144440		2500ft.			Heading towards plume
144338	R12	2500ft.			fire on left - photos taken.
					winds 10ms ⁻¹ / 324°
					343 122 knts
154552					In plume + base of cloud.
154600					cloud phys. ⁷⁵⁰ → 2500 cc.
					10 delayed increase 140ppb.
					for just a second.
					AMS soot (unburned)
154819	R13	2000ft.			hydrocarbons)
154818	R	2000ft.	331		In plume.
					wind 7ms ⁻¹ / 335°
					331 116
					aerosol 4 ⁰⁰⁰ → 4500 counts.
155006					Ontop of fire

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		2000ft.			dem peak 228 CO
155048	R2end				Turning left to go back
155051	R3end	2000ft.			through smoke.
					Cloud phys 4000 → 5000 conts.
155204					Fire to left.
		2000ft.	168	51.6/10.5	PCASP ~ 6000 conts.
					Turning left back to
					source
					wind 10ms ⁻¹ / 327°
					T 1.2, T _D -1.15
155347	R14	2000ft.			Entering plume.
					slight turn to go right along plume
					aerosol increase to 5000
					CO to 190 ppb. (few seconds delay)
155433					aerosol 5500 cc ^{maybe inst} _{location}
		2000ft.	322	51.7/10.4	T 1.26, T _D -0.7C.
					winds: 8 / 334°
					CP1 large blobs ~ 10-50 μm
					PCASP ~ 10000 plus
					AMS - soot mty
					CO ~ 200 ppb.
					NOx ~ 2 ppb. larger at of plume.
					SO2 ~ 1.5 ppb.
	R1end				Returning to Cranfield.

~16:15

Land.

 CN ^{max} ~~10000~~ 20000
 everything stayed below cloud.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Edges SI.0/0.6W
~~124120~~ 124120
 SI.1/0.7W
 1min46 124306
 (15°-20°)
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MISSION SCIENTIST 2: STUART NEWMAN

Flight No **B.149**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115918					TAKE OFF
1209	R1	F2090	165	SI.0W SI.7N	Smoke plume to port Wind 9ms ⁻¹ / 11 deg
121430	"	F2090	164	SI.4N 0.8W	Wind 12ms ⁻¹ / 29 deg Passed plume source to port O3 50ppb CO 112 ppb CNC 350 / cm ⁻³
1220	"	"	152	SI.1N 0.6W	Wind 12ms ⁻¹ / 34 deg
1224	"	F2090	90	SI.N 0.3W	Wind 13ms ⁻¹ / 46 deg CNC 571 / O3 49 / CO 115 Heading eastwards south of source
1228	End R1 P↓	F2090 to F2060			
123238	R2	6000'	271	SI.0N 0.1E	Wind 14ms ⁻¹ / 24° CNC 568 / O3 52 / CO 120
1236	"	"	282	SI.0N 0.1W	Wind 13ms ⁻¹ / 19° CNC 548 / O3 52 / CO 120
1241	"	6000'	339	SI.1N 0.6W	CNC 582 / O3 51 / CO 120 Winds 13ms ⁻¹ / 15°
124452	R2	Inter.			Held in orbit
124905	"	Reconn.	340	SI.2 0.7	
1301	"		349	SI.8N 1.0W	Wind 10ms ⁻¹ / 357°
130402	End R2 P↓				CNC 617 / O3 50 / CO 121
1307~30	R3	5000'	162	SI.9N 1.0W	CNC 582 / O3 49 / CO [cal] Winds 12ms ⁻¹ / 349

Cat. (4)
 Essex from NATS

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
131330	R3	5000'	167	51.6N 0.9W	Winds 13ms ⁻¹ / 353° CNC 332/O ₃ 48 / CO 108
1317	"	"	155	51.4N 0.8W	Turn towards Midhurst Winds 11ms ⁻¹ / 354° CNC 341 / O ₃ 50 / CO 108
131830	"	"	154	51.3N 0.8W	Plume visible to port (east) but source may be extinguished
132130					Approaching edge of plume
132230				51.0N 0.6W	Edge of plume, below us
132311	"	"			Turning, in middle of it Wind 12ms ⁻¹ / 22° PCASP ↑ 5000 from 100
132430	"	5000'	090	51.0N 0.4W	Seem to have passed over; no great change in O ₃ , CO CNC up to ~4000
132826	end R3	5000'		51.0N 0.1W	Turning, in cloud at 4000'
133125	R4	4000'	281	50.9N 0.1W	CNC 4000 / O ₃ 34 / CO [car] Winds 5ms ⁻¹ / 29° ↑NO _x by 4ppb
1334			298	50.9N 0.3W	In cloud tops
133630					In edge of pollution, soft above cloud tops
133714					Into main plume 0.5µm sizes
133739					Out of it
133915	"	4000'	358	51.1N 0.6W	CO ↓ from 200 to 120, O ₃ 40ppb Winds 6ms ⁻¹ / 11°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.149**
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **13/12/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1344	R4	4000'	339	Sl. 3N 0.8W	Winds 6ms ⁻¹ / 358° CNC baseline ~350/cc CO 108 ppb, O3 44 ppb
1350					Turn onto flight leg at 3000'
134907	end R4				↑ Sulphate in boundary layer
135132	R5	3000'	159	Sl. 4N 0.8W	Winds 10ms ⁻¹ / 342° CNC 5000 (cloud) CO 136 / O3 25 ppb
1359	"	"	158	Sl. 1N 0.7W	Nearing plume CNC 7000 CO 144 / O3 30 ppb
1400-01				Sl. 0W 0.6W	Appear to be sitting underneath. Max 7 ppb NOx 145 ppb CO
1404					CO 150+ ppbv 900-1000 Cloud Phys. aerosol
1407	R5	3000'	084	Sl. 0N 0.0E	Winds 6ms ⁻¹ / 356° O3 21 / CO 201 / CNC 8000
1410	"	"	088	Sl. 0 0.2E	Winds 7ms ⁻¹ / 4deg CNC 5170 / O3 34 / CO 142 ≤ 1µg/m ³ organics AMS PCASP has shown 500-600/cc, occasionally 1000/cc, but not higher even within plume
141244	end R5				
141702	R6	2000'	280	Sl. 0N 0.1W	(1870ft) CNC ~10,000 CO 177, O3 27 ppb
1423		"		Sl. 0N 0.3W	PSAP abs coeff ↑, <u>Windy</u> PCASP ↑ 1500 or so CO ~150, O3 ~29 Winds 7.5ms ⁻¹ / 1°

Peak in CNC ~15000/cm³

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1426			336	51.0N 0.6W	Winds 6ms ⁻¹ / 351° CO 159 / O ₃ 20 / CNC 8000
143552	end R6	2000'		51.6N 0.9W	Climb to 4000'
	R7	4000'	142	51.5 1.0W	CNC 2850, skirting tops of cloud. CO down to 115, O ₃ ~43 ppb
144440	"	4000'	156	51.2N 0.7W	Winds 11ms ⁻¹ / 337° CO 109 / O ₃ 45 / CNC 1150 still close to cloud tops
144730			149	51.1N 0.6W	Edge of plume below
1451			090	51.0N 0.3W	CO ↑ ~180 O ₃ ↓ ~20 ppb PCASP showing increase too
145628	end R7	4000'			
145822	R8	4500'	288	50.9N 0.0E	Winds 11ms ⁻¹ / 18° CNC 398 / CO down 110 / O ₃ 50 ppb SO/ce particle conc. Heading back closer to Kemel Hempstead
1507			005	51.1N 0.5W	CNC 435 / O ₃ 50 / CO 112 ppbv
1510			001	51.2N 0.6W	Winds 10ms ⁻¹ / 3° CNC 667 / cm ³ / O ₃ 51 / CO 114 ppbv PCASP 30-50 ↑ 100 Above cloud tops
1513	R8	"	000	51.4N 0.6W	Winds 10ms ⁻¹ / 3°
151345					CNC 650 / O ₃ 50 / CO 116
1517		~5500'	000	51.6N 0.6W	
151830	R9	4500'	359	51.7N 0.6W	CNC 674 / O ₃ 50 / CO 118
1521	"	"	357	51.8N 0.6W	Winds 11ms ⁻¹ / 350° CNC 770 / O ₃ 50 / CO 118 ppbv

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1524	R9	4500'	606	51.9 N 0.5 W	In holding pattern near Cranfield
1528		"	030	52.2 N 0.4 W	North of smoke source awaiting instructions re: permission to fly closer to source
					CO = 114 O ₃ = 50 ppb CNC = 860/cm ³
1535		4500'	213	52.1 N 0.5 W	Winds 13ms ⁻¹ / 339°
153634	R10	4000'	163	52.0 N 0.5 W	Winds 14ms ⁻¹ / 332° CNC 730 / CO 113 / O ₃ 50 ppb
	end R10				
		3500'			Run over top of source
153936	R11	"	166	51.7 N 0.4 W	Mile to left of source CO ~ 124 O ₃ ~ 39 CNC 1560 (but in cloud)
154053		3500'			Turn to right Winds 14ms ⁻¹ / 336°
154135	↓	3000'			
	Start	3000'	266	51.6 N 0.5 W	Winds 9ms ⁻¹ / 347°
154300					Right turn towards S. side before drop to 2500'
				51.6 N 0.6 W	Just in bottom of cloud
154418	on run 12	2500'	099	51.7 N 0.5 W	Heading directly for plume Winds 9ms ⁻¹ / 329°
154554					In plume now Big ↑ aerosol 1000-2500 PCAST
154640		end 2000'			CO only ~ 140 ppbv (response time?) AMS "soot"
154815	R13	2000'	332	51.6 N 0.3 W	CO ↑ 150+, approaching line

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: Operator: DRS time: DAU1 time: DAU2 time: DAU3 time: AUX1 time: AUX2 time: Page 2 of 2

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
133125	300	0.2	409	5000		10	50									Start brun 4	
1334	400	0.2	1010	7000		10	25										
1337	2000	0.09	1327														
1340	70	0.09	1423	10													
1342	30	0.08	1430														
1345	30	0.08	1430														
1348	25	0.08	1430														
134907																End run 4	
	350	0.09	1540	100												Start run 5	
1354	175	0.13	1593	1000													
1357	150	0.1	1761	80													
1359	200	0.09	1762	80													
1400	350	0.09	1762	80													
1402	450	0.09															
1403	950	0.09	1762	80													
1405	700	0.09	1762	80													
1407	750	0.09	1762	80													
1410	550	0.09	1762	80													
1413	600	0.08	1762	80													
141702																Start run 6	
1418	600	0.09	1762	80													
1422	1200	0.1	1762	80													
1425	500	0.09	1762	80													
1427	500	0.09	1762	80													
1429	500	0.09	1762	80													
1433	350	0.09	1762	80													
1436																	
144																Start run 7 @ 040	
1441	100	0.08	1881														
1443	50	0.08	1881														
1445	50	0.08	1968														
1448	30	0.08	1991														
1450	40	0.15	2014														
1452	1000	0.12	2165														
1455	350	0.09	2355														
145726																End run 7	
145822	30	0.08	2520													Start run 8	
1501	40	0.08	2520														
1503	40	0.08	2520														
1505	80	0.09	2520														
1507	80	0.08	2520														
1510	80	0.06	2520														
1512	100	0.09	2520														
151325	130	0.09	2520													End run 8	
1519	130	0.08														Recommence 8	
1521	150	0.07	2520														

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B149**Date:** 13/12/05

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	Y	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	Y	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	Y	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	Y	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL_19112005.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour -10800 NOTE THAT FFSSP CLOCK WAS OUT BY 3 HOURS
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	Y	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto -4
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?	Y	
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B149

Date: 13/12/05

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit	Y	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written Bad reads = 0
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	110000 170000
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product		This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10	Y	Done for 1 and 10 sec
iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC	Y	
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter	Y	
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	In O:\CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D	Y	120000 161000 Note the particle type 8
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	Y	
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	Y	
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B149**Date:** 13/12/05

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown	Y	Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate 1
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat' ,pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' iii) exit	Y	
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	Y	MFDB

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B149	Date	13/12/05	Operator(s)	DRK	log page	1	of	6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

115544									SET TIME (FROM HORACE)
115741									Set JACK VIEW
115805	PRE	T/O	90° AFT	500	500				Start Measurement (Test)
115826									Stop
→ 115913									T/O confirmed
120016									Start Dark View
120040	TRANSIT	144ft	90° A	750	1000				Start Measurement
120154									Start Dark View [Sample period
120218	"	52kft	177° (A) ↓	750	1000				Start Measurement [1 sec]
									[Temp +13°C]
120839	R1.	FL090	"	750	1000				Start R1. (A →) [+14°C] All Peltiers on.
121414									← Measure Dark View (x2).
121437									Restart Measurement. (well above snake at this level)
121650		START	CAMERA TAKE #1						000). (looking downwards) (+13°C)
121920									Over field (q. extensive) of Sc below. Dark View (A) ←
122033	R1.	FL090	177° (A) ↓	1000	1000				Restart Measurement [Sample Period] 1.00 sec
122142									Point B. now (c/h). [Temp +13°C]
1224									→ V. bright spectra from Sc field underneath. (clipping on vis especially)
122537									Start Dark (A) ←
122603	R1.	FL090	177° (A) ↓	1000	1000				Start Measurement
1227-28	end								[Manual] Adjust SWS ← to point 160° then 140° AFT from Bright Tree on VIS THAN NOIR.]
122925	R1	FL090	177° (A) ↓	1000 " "	1000 " "				END RUN 1 [Sample period 1 sec] [Temp +13°C]

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 14C	Date	13/12/05	Operator(s)	DK	log page	2 of 6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

123157						←	Start Dark Current view } clipping
123207						←	Start Measurement }
123240	Run 2	6000' (5.3kft)	17FA (↓)	1000	1000		Start R2. [Sample period 1.00sec] [Temp +12°C] Wind 010 / 27kt - FLIGHT DECK Horace 019 / 14 m/sec
123719	Run 2	6000' (5.3kft)	17FA (↓)	250	750		Start Dark Current view (x2) } Adjusting Start Measurement } Integ ² times
124045			→				In Turn, going over plume as roll out No 'plume' evidence on C. Physics or Core Chem.
124315			→				Coming over Plume edge
124410			→				Start Dark Measurement. - [Temp +12°C]
124422							Start Measurement
124452			→				Interrupt R2 for 1 circuit to avoid other air traffic
124905	Run 2	6000'	17FA (↓)	250	750		Resume R2 at 6000' [Sample period 1.0 sec ; Temp +12°C]
125235						←	Start Dark View (Mainly new plane or clouds below)
125245	"	"	"	500	750		Start Measurement.
125320							o/h Woodley, heading for Juvetry
1255						←	[Temp +11°C] Peltiers 1 & 2 off]
1301							←
130200							←
130213	Run 2	6000'	17FA (↓)	250	750		Start Measurement (Some Se layer T/S below - otherwise clear)
130402	End R2	6000'	"	"	"		End R2 (Turning 2) [T/S Ci above]
130705						←	Descending for 500' Start Dark Current View
130718							Start Measurement [Temp +14
130729	Start R3	5000'	17FA (↓)	250	750		Start R3 A → D [ALL Peltiers on]
130910							RESET TIME FROM HORACE

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 144	Date	13/12/05	Operator(s)	JOK	log page	3 of 6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

1311	→	5000' (1070mb) (+3kft 1013mb)		250	750	Wind 352/12 wsec Helix on this run at 5000'
131736	R3	5000'	174(A) ↓	250	750	1000 Start Measurement [Sample Period 1sec] (Temp +13°C) Dark Current views (x2) ^{generally} Now cloud of cloud below - Reset Integ. Times
132255						Dark Current view
132308	R3	5000'	"	250	750	Measurement start.
1323	→					o/h Midwest, turning for Maxfield (PTC)
132826	R3	5000'	174(A) ↓	250	750	End R3 & Turning, descend to 4000' [Sample 1sec] for Run 4.
133100						change to ↑ view now manually
133125	Start R4	4000'				Start R4 [SWS Temp +13°C]
133154						Dark current view
133203	R4	4000'	006(F) ↑	250	750	Start Measurement [Sample Period 1sec]
133400						In cloud tops along this run
133620	→					Out of cloud tops now. (250 below us) ^{See top}
133710	→					Into main plane now (1 layer above us just below cloud top)
133740	→					Out of plane.
133833	→					Into cloud tops again now. [PTC ~ 1/2 way]
134019						Dark current view (mainly above cloud).
134034	R4	4000'	006(F) ↑	400	1000	Start Measurement
134420						Some Sc just below; ^{B-70 then Ci above}
134518						At point B, B → A. [+13°C]
134616	→					Change view to ↓ rest of run & Start Dark Current
134628						Start Measurement
134715	End R4	4000'	174(A) ↓	400	1000	End R4 Descend to 3000'; Turn to ↑ view
135046						Start Dark View
135105			006(F)	250	1000	Start Measurement.
135132	Start R5	3000'	006(F)	250	1000	Start R5.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B149** Date **13/12/05** Operator(s) **DRK** log page **4** of **6**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

~ 135430						o/h Woodley
135738						o/h Farnborough. the W-WAY.
135755	LWS	3000'	006(F)	250	1000	Generally in under clouds. on this run [SWS TEMP +12°C]
140105						Under plane now.
140158						Turning at Pt C for Pt D
140327						Start DarkView C Wind 385/8m/sec. (Heads)
140339	LWS	3000'	006(F)	500	1000	Start Measurement C → now. Aerosols ↑ 900/cc. [Temp +12°C]
140627						Chemistry generally 'high' values.
140943						At Pt D, but continuing E beyond Pt D to see if chemistry/aerosols "drop off". Aerosols 600/cc for last 1.5-2 mins.
141244	End RS	3000'	006(F)	500	1000	End RS, turn ↻ return 3000'
141345						DarkView C [SWS TEMP +12°C]
141357		"	"	"	"	Start Measurement
~ 141540						Now can descent to 2000' for ↻
141703	Start R6	2000'	006(F)	500	1000	Start R6.
		(1.3xH 0.13mb)				(Sample Period 1.00sec)
~ 142230						Aerosols .900 ↑ 1500/cc now [Temp +11°C, RH 127%]
142650						DarkView C
142701	R6	"	"	"	"	Start Measurement
143100						Under Sc now (fairly continuous).
1435						Running into cloud
143559	End R6	2000'	006(F)	500	1000	End R6 b.c./mb ↑ 900' soon.
143617						DarkView C
143628						Start Measurement

.1530 LAMP.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 149	Date	13/12/05		Operator(s)	JRK		log page	5 of 6	
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks				
				Vis	NIR					

143915									Manoeuvring (just above cloud here)		
14395	Start Run 7	4500'	006° (F)	500	1000				Start Run 7		
144130									Change from ↑ to ↓ view as we're above Sc (just). (Before looking ↑ on previous 4500' run.)		
144243									Dark Measurement Cal		
144257	Run 7	4500'	174° (A)	750	1000				Start Measurement		
144425									↓ (Sample Point → 1.00sec) Into cloud (for ~30-40 sec)		
									[Temp +14°C ALL PARTICLES ON]		
144842									Wind 340/7m/sec (Hence) Midwest, turning C → D.		
145110									Into cloud. CO ↑ CO ₂ ↓		
145315									} 2 minutes of interesting Chemistry → (excellent anticorrel ⁿ)		
145517									Start Dark Cal (Current View)		
145528									Start Measurement		
145628	End R 7	4500'	174° (A)	750	1000				End Run 7. Climb ↑ 4500' return to Midwest → C, (4500' then go Midwest → Cranfield)		
									↓ (Sample Point 1.00 sec)		
145823	Start R 8	4500'	174° (A)	750	1000				Start Run 8 D → C (Above cloud layer)		
									↓		
150447									Dark Current View [Temp +14°C]		
150501	Run 8	4500'	174° (A)	1000	1000				Measurement restarted.		
150600									→ (Sample Point 1 sec) Midwest beacon now turning & will transit Midwest → Cranfield during Hensel Hensstead to str d.		
151325									End R 8. & Climb.		
151408									Start Current View (Dark)		
151420									Start Measurement		
151530									→ SWS OFF (2h 58m 41sec - not another fix ? Reg'd)		
151718									Tape Descending ↓ back to 4500'		
151810	Restart R 8	4500'	174° (A)	1000	1000				Restart R 8		
152400									→ RECORD ANOTHER CANEX TAPE (Many prolong flight by up to another 1 hour, near to H. Hensstead)		

1451 -
1456
increased CO
mix ratio
increased O₃
mix ratio]

~

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 149	Date	13/12/05	Operator(s)	JOK	log page	6 of 6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

153450	-		174°(A)	1000	1000	Manoeuvring, can go back over plane. Discussing best heights for run.
1536			↓			Descending to 4000'. ^{SUSTEMP} [+13C]
153633	Start 12	4000'	"	"	"	Start Run 9
		(3.4kft 10320)				
153738	"	"	174°(A)	1000	1000	Start Dark Current View
153750	"	"	↓	"	"	Start Measurement
153907						End Run, descend to 3500'.
15392						Into cloud
153930	Start 12	3500'	"	"	"	Start Run (in cloud tops)
154135	End					Descend to 3000'
	Start 11					
154250		3000'				Change ↓ to ↑ View, turn & descend to 2500'
154241						← Start Dark View
154253						Start Measurement
154348	R 12	2500'	006°(A)	1000	1000	Start Run 12 Wind 340/22-A/C 327/10-H/ICE
154557			↑			↳ into plane now.
154640	R 12	2500'	"	"	"	End Run 12 Descend to 2000' for another run thro' plane.
154825	Start R 13	2000'	"	"	"	JOK Cal / RESTRICT MEASUREMENT HOLD [SUSTEMP +13C]
155018						o/h plane.
155048	R 13	2000'	"	"	"	
						Final Run coming up (2000')
						Change View ↑ to ↓ (to see fire/smoke?)
155244						→ Dark View Cal
155255						→ Start Measurement
155347	Start 14	2000'	174°(A)	"	"	(8500/CC PLASP ARROW)
(no 1555 →) View	00:29:30 → 00:31:00		↓			on SWS CRIMSON Tape looking ↓ (Small Files smoke)
155645						Final JOK Cal
155659			174°(A)	"	"	Final Measurement mode

160114 SWS OFF ↓ RTB.

[off 155920 (35 m 20 sec)]
Tape II

161013 → LAND CLEARFIELD.

115913

+ 1100

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 149

Date: 13th December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	N	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JO1D	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
“ JO1D	N	AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	n	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	Y
CO	Y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B149

Date: 13th December 2005

Instruments

Aircraft

None!

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B149:

Log	Reason
Brief	Basic way Point version only
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CCN	No operator listed so no log though Flight Manager's Instrument Status shows instrument as being switched on.

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	3 Apr 2006	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing Cloud Physics flight log in addition to above
r1	6 Apr 2006	Doug Anderson	Cloud Physics log added
r2	12 Feb 2007	Doug Anderson	PSAP log added

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras

4 x Down/Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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